

PRANAYAMA - THE 'PRAN' FOR WOMEN IN POLLUTED CITIES

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INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has emerged as one of the most serious environmental and public health challenges in modern metropolitan cities. Rapid urbanization, industrial growth, increasing vehicular emissions, construction activities, and population pressure have significantly deteriorated air quality in major metro-polluting cities. Gases like nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, and prolonged exposure to such polluted air has wide-ranging effects on human health, the environment, and the overall quality of urban life. One of the most severe consequences of poor Air Quality Index is its impact on human health, particularly the respiratory system. Continuous exposure to polluted air irritates the airways and lungs, leading to coughing, breathlessness, and chest discomfort. It significantly increases the risk of chronic respiratory diseases such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, bronchitis, and lung infections. Children and the elderly are especially vulnerable, as their immune and respiratory systems are weaker. In children, long-term exposure can impair lung development, while in older adults it can worsen existing health conditions.

Poor air quality also affects the Cardio Vascular system and increasing the risk of heart attacks, strokes, high blood pressure, and irregular heartbeats. Studies have shown that people living in highly polluted metropolitan cities often have a reduced life expectancy due to prolonged exposure to toxic air. Additionally, air pollution has been linked to headaches, fatigue, reduced concentration, anxiety, and other mental health issues.

The aim of the WHO Chronic Respiratory Diseases Programme is to support Member States in reducing morbidity, disability, and premature mortality associated with cardio vascular diseases.

Yoga an Ancient Indian system of Philosophy found to play an important role in prevention, maintain and promotion of health. Scriptures related to Yoga reveals that its practice leads to inner evolution and understanding of one's own inner self leading to total transformation in Individuals consciousness. "Prana" is the vital life force; without Prana, there is no life. Prana is not oxygen itself, but it requires oxygen to function. When this life force is brought under conscious control known as "Ayam", it produces remarkable effects, and this regulated process is called "Pranayama." 'Pranayama' immense power of Prana, nature has entrusted the act of breathing not entirely too human will, but largely to the autonomic nervous system, ensuring that this vital force is not misused. The process of breathing is closely connected to the rhythms of our physical, mental, and emotional life. It is based on the principle that when the breath is unsteady, the mind is also unsteady, and when the breath is calm, the mind becomes calm. According to the Hathapradeepika, the practice of Pranayama helps eliminate impurities and waste products from both the body and the mind. Many research studies reported that, regular practice of Pranayama strengthens the respiratory muscles, improves lung function, and enhances oxygen intake. Techniques such as *Anulom Vilom*, *Bhastrika*, and *Kapalbhati* help cleanse the air passages and improve breathing efficiency.

To find out the effect of the Pranayama on Cardio Vascular Endurance a Pranayama program considering various forms of Pranayama like Anulom-Vilom Pranayama, Suryabhedhan Pranayama, Sheetkari Pranayama, Sheetal Pranayama, Bhramari Pranayama and Ujjayi Pranayama was prepared. Details of the methodology, sample, and results of this study are presented below."

METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design**

For the present study, Pre-test Post-test Control Group design of the True Experimental research was used. As per the design, data of Cardio Vascular Endurance was collected before and after the manipulated Pranayama' training intervention.

- **Sampling**

Fifty women (n = 50) aged between 35 and 50 years were randomly selected from Junagar, Navi Mumbai. All participants were associated with the club run by the Senior Citizen Centre of Junagar, Navi Mumbai. The selected participants were further randomly divided into two groups: a Control Group (n = 25) and an Experimental Group (n = 25). Women in the Experimental Group underwent a manipulated Pranayama training intervention for 30 minutes daily over a period of six weeks, excluding Sundays. The Control Group did not receive any

Pranayama training intervention. Both groups were allowed to continue their routine daily activities throughout the study period. Control over variables such as dietary habits, medication use, and daily routine was beyond the scope of the experiment.

- **Collection of Data**

Prior to the intervention and after the intervention 12 Minute Run/Walk Test was used to collect the data of Cardio Vascular Endurance of the selected sample.

RESULT ON CARDIO VASCULAR ENDURANCE

Table 1

Pre-Test and Post-Test Mean Scores, Standard Deviation, and Sample Size (N) of the Control and Experimental Groups on Cardio Vascular Endurance.

Groups	Tests	Mean	Std. Dev.	N
Control Group	Pre-Test	1070.16	56.452	25
	Post-Test	1091.60	57.163	25
Experimental Group	Pre-Test	1095.28	55.012	25
	Post-Test	1141.00	77.032	25

In Table-1, it can be seen that the mean scores of pre-test and post-test of *Cardio Vascular Endurance* of Control Group is 1070.16 and 1091.60 respectively, whereas the standard deviation score of pre-test is 56.452 and the post-test score is 57.163. In case of Experimental Group the mean score of pre-test is 1095.28 and the post-test mean score is 1141.00, standard deviation of the same is 55.012 and 77.032 serially. The sample size (n = 25) remains consistent across both the groups in both the pre-test and post-test, ensuring equal representation and minimizing any discrepancies that could arise from unequal sample sizes.

Table 2

Comparison of Cardio Vascular Endurance between the Control Group and the Experimental Group in the Pre-test and Post-test.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Control & Experimental Groups	34707.69	1	34707.69	9.01	.003	$p < 0.05^*$
Pre-test Post-Test	28190.41	1	28190.41	7.31	.008	$p < 0.05^*$
Error	369950.40	96	3853.650			
Total	121328757.0	100				
Corrected Total	436532.99	99				

It can be seen that in the above Table 2, in case of the comparison between the Control Group and Experimental Group the value of Sum of Squares and Mean Square is 34707.69 with the 'df' value 1. The value of 'F' ratio is 9.01 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05^*$), thus the stated null hypothesis that 'there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the Control Group and Experimental Group with respect to Cardio Vascular Endurance' is rejected and the objective that 'to compare the mean scores between the Control Group, and Experimental Group with respect to Cardio Vascular Endurance' is achieved.

In above table 2, in case of the comparison of Pre-test, Post-test of Cardio Vascular Endurance the value of Sum of Squares and Mean Square is 28190.41 with the 'df' value 1. The value of 'F' ratio is 7.31 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance ($p < 0.05^*$), thus the stated null hypothesis that 'there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the Pre-test and Post-test with respect to Cardio Vascular Endurance is rejected.

Based on the obtained results, it can be inferred that the Control Group, and Experimental Group as well as the pre-test and post-test scores of Cardio Vascular Endurance, statistically differ significant from one another.

Figure 1

Mean Scores of Pre-test and Post-test of Control Group and Experimental Group of Cardio Vascular Endurance.

CONCLUSION

Overall, based on the obtained results, it can be interpreted that the post-test score of Cardio Vascular Endurance of Experimental Group is significantly improved. Therefore, it can be says that the manipulated Pranayama intervention is helpful to improve the Cardio Vascular Endurance of the Women of Navi Mumbai.

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